

THEORIES ABOUT THE ORIGIN AND FORMATION OF LANGUAGE

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Abstract: This article deals with analyzing language and its development. Some linguists think this development is related to increases in brain volume, while others view language structures as being adapted for particular communicative and cultural functions. In addition to this language is a formal system of signs governed by grammar rules for combining to express meaning. It is emphasized in this definition that the human language can be described as a closed structural system composed of rules providing for certain signs and their specific meanings.

Keywords: language, sign language, sound, human language, semiotics, oral language, manual language, tactile language

Language is a form of speech, consisting of grammar and vocabulary. In spoken and written languages as well as those which may be used in sign language, it is an essential means of communicating the meaning. The main purpose of language is to unite people and start the engine of life. [1] Writing systems that allow for the recording and preservation of sounds or signs of languages have developed in a large majority of human languages. Human language is characterised by significant differences in cultural and historical diversity between cultures and time. In human languages, there are the properties of productivity and displacement, which allow them to build up an endless string of sentences as well as a capacity for referring to objects, events or ideas that have not yet arisen in conversation. Human language is based upon conventions, which can be acquired by learning. The scope of language is only words, and phrases it is measured not only by words but also by the lexical meanings of words.[2] Language is spoken, signed or both: all languages can be encoded in the secondary media using tactile, visual and audible stimuli such as write, whistling, singing and braille. Language is a system of words and grammar used by the people of a particular country or area. [18]In each language, signs are tied to specific meanings by a process known as semiotics. Oral, manual and tactile languages contain a phonological system that governs how symbols are used to form sequences known as words or morphemes and a syntactic system that governs how words and morphemes are combined to form phrases and utterances. Linguistic Studies are the scientific study of languages. Language ideology is often interpreted as conceptual or ideational, referring to consciousness, beliefs, conceptions, and ideas. The most frequently cited quality of ideology is its tight relationship to social authority and its legitimation.[5]At least since the time of Gorgias and Plato in ancient Greek civilization, critical linguistic examinations have been discussed such as the philosophy of language, relationships between speech and thoughts, how words represent experience, etc. Latin, such as Italian, Spanish and Portuguese, and some other Indo-European languages, especially Slavic languages and also Dutch and German but this never happens nearly in Uzbek language from Turkic group. [3]Arguments have been made that languages come from emotion, including those of Jean Jacques Rousseau and Immanuel Kant who argued that language comes from reason and logic.

The fact that philosophy is a study of language itself was argued in the twentieth century by philosophers such as Ludwig Wittgenstein, 1889–1951. Ferdinand de Saussure and Noam Chomsky have emerged as major figures in the current language of these times. When early hominins acquired the ability to form a theory of mind and shared intentionality, language is thought to have evolved gradually from earlier primate communication systems. Some linguists believe that this process is associated with brain volume growth, and some see language structures evolving to meet particular linguistic functions such as communication or social function. In our brains, language is processed from a wide range of places, especially in Broca and Wernicke. In early childhood, people learn to speak through social interaction, and children are usually able to speak fluently by age three. Language and culture are dependent on each other. So language also has social uses, such as the identification of group identities, societal stratagems and use for grooming and entertainment, which are in addition to its purely communicational purposes. In time, languages evolve and change; the history of their development can be reconstructed through an examination of modern languages to determine which traits their ancestors must have had for these later developmental stages to occur. A typological classification group languages into types according to their structural characteristics which are several main group classifications. [13] A formal language in this respect is a set of signs for the processing and decoding of information, as opposed to traditional human languages. As natural human languages are studied in the area of linguistics, this article deals specifically with their properties. The audience's role is very important. [6,7,8] It means language should be suitable for listeners. "Language" has two main meanings as an object of linguistic study: an abstract concept, such as "French", and a specific linguistic system. The Swiss linguist Ferdinand de Saussure, who defined the modern discipline of linguistics, first explicitly formulated the distinction using the French word *langage* for language as a concept, *langue* as a specific instance of a language system, and *parole* for the concrete usage of speech in a particular language. It became fashionable to speculate about the origin of languages during Enlightenment debates on man's origins. Thinkers such as Rousseau and Johann Gottfried Herder argued that language had originated in the instinctive expression of emotions and that it was originally closer to music and poetry than to the logical expression of rational thought. In the late twentieth century, philosophers began to ask whether language had any role in shaping our experience of the world and whether it was simply a reflection of its objective character or created concepts that in turn imposed structure upon how we experienced an objective world. This led to the question of whether philosophical problems are firstly linguistic problems. According to one definition, language is the mental force that allows people to engage in linguistic activities: learning languages and producing and understanding words. The listener unknowingly befriends the speaker this is the purpose of the speaker. [9,10]

Even though the language classrooms becoming more communicative, most of the teachers still teach grammar explicitly (Lee and VanPatten, 1995). We think it is not a problem as the deductive approach can also be applied effectively if a teacher is competent enough. [4] This definition stresses the universality of language to all humans and emphasizes the biological basis for the human capacity for language as a unique human brain development. In linguistic studies, these types of concepts are commonly used within the framework of cerebral sciences and neurolinguistics. While the field of psycholinguistics studies how people use language to

express and meet their individual needs, the field of sociolinguistics studies the use of language in society.[17] Interlocutors intend to communicate for different purposes, so that inform, declare ask, persuade, direct, complain, describe and can exchange information with intonation, degrees of loudness, tempo, and other non-representational or paralinguistic aspects of vocalization to convey meaning.[9]

The second definition refers to language as an informal system of signs governed by combinational syntax to express meaning. It stresses that human languages may be considered closed Structural Systems composed of rules relating to specific signs and their respective meanings. Ferdinand de Saussure first introduced the structuralist view of language to a wide range of linguistic approaches, and his Structuralism has remained fundamental for them all. Some advocates of Saussure's view argue that the formal approach to language structure, identifying its basic elements and then producing a formal account of rules based on which these elements are combined to form words and sentences, is appropriate. The main proponent of such a theory is Noam Chomsky, the originator of the generative theory of grammar, who has defined language as the construction of sentences that can be generated using transformational grammar. In short, the nativist Noam Chomsky stated that children are born with a means of language acquisition and that they understand the language code of the people around them and adapt to that language.[12] New sciences have the same subject matter of investigation – interrelation and interaction of (native/foreign) speaker and his language, on the one hand, thinking (thought) and culture, on the other, which results in the cognition of the world (the objective reality).[15] In our society, people communicate through a variety of means. We connect the letters and the sounds to each other and apply the events of our psyche to the masses. Society is a collection of different worldviews and spirits. [11]. Everyone has their expectations and hopes. That is why one main character in one story written by Guy De Maupassant thinks like this. I would not be alone anymore because we would play and speak with him. [16] Currently, representatives of many fields are studying how language is manifested and realized in public. The composition of the language is being studied through a combination of many fields. In particular, the fact that language is considered together with psychology, philosophy, political science and social science is a clear example of this. Undoubtedly, the most difficult aspect of learning is the analysis of the relationship between the mental and speech processes of a person. In this case, a person receives foreign information from the external environment and returns it to the public through mutual analysis through his psychic and mental abilities.

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